

A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF CLUB ACTIVITIES IN DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS), PERAMBALUR

N. Suguna*, B. Sainisha** & M. Rasika**

* Assistant Professor, Department of MBA, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

** II Year Student, Department of Management Studies, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract:

The project report titled "A Study on Effectiveness of Club Activities in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur". The sample constitutes the students belonging to different departments. The data's were collected from primary sources. Primary data was collected through an administered questionnaire with twenty five questions. sampling technique was done to draw the sample size of 110 respondents from the 280 students. The objective considered for the study were to know the participation level, awareness and utilization level of the students provided by institution. From the analysis, it is concluded that most of the students are satisfied with the club activities are increasing their participation level. The students are effectively utilize the club activities.

Key Words: Club Activities, Participation Level, Effective Utilization of Club Activities, Improving Skills and Knowledge.

Introduction:

Besides, teaching work in the school or college time one other activity which is known as of the development of the student. These activities also keep the student busy which help in maintaining the discipline in the school or college. Game, sports, cultural performance, debates, dramas, scouting, N.C.C., N.S.S. etc. are some of the co- curricular activities. Club activities are co-curricular and provide an opportunity to the students to know their skills and also to enjoy the college work. These activities are related with the society and the community at large. Some people think that these are extra activities, but it is no so. These activities are part of the vast curriculum of the school and college studies. They develop the personality of the students and also provide the knowledge of the past, the hidden qualities of the students. Activities which complement but are not part of the conventional academic curriculum. It means that Co-curricular activities are those activities which fall outside the regular academic curriculum yet they are a part of schooling or collegiate life. These are observed in tandem with an institute's curriculum and have a yearly schedule. Most of the educational organizations in various different parts of the world facilitate these activities for school and college students.

Co-curricular activities exist at all levels of education, from primary, secondary-higher secondary school, college and university education. These activities are compulsory in some institutions while in other it's voluntary. Where these are compulsory all students must participate them alongside the standard study curriculum. At higher levels of education student participations generally include academic points in lieu of the efforts put by a student in a particular activity. These are held outside standard curriculum hours and the activities partaken depend on the nature of the institute and occasion.

Review of the Literature:

According to Zill, Nord, and Loomis (2013), participation in co -curricular activities improves an adolescent's chances of avoiding such risky behaviors as dropping out, becoming a teenage parent, engaging in delinquency, smoking or abusing drugs or alcohol through three mechanisms. National Federation of State High School Associations [NFHS] of America (1999) had stated that co- curricular activities are an extension of not a diversion from, a good educational program and support the academic mission of the school. Students who participate in activity programs tend to have higher grade point averages, better attendance records, lower dropout rates and fewer discipline problems than students who don't participate.

Allison (2010) found out that students who participate in co-curricular activities not only do better academically than students who do not but also develop other facets of their personalities in the process. Self-esteem, self - confidence, social cooperation, and leadership skills are just a few of the cognitive factors that are affected. Co-curricular activities allow students to blend aspects of their academic learning into personal actions

Wagner (2011) found out that Co-curricular activities encourage personal accomplishments and the development of interpersonal skills. Adolescents who participate in these activities have opportunities to assume

meaningful roles and responsibilities. The sense of efficacy student's gain from these experiences can be an important protective factor for those growing up the circumstances.

Objectives of the Study:

- A study on "Effectiveness of club activities "among students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.
- To analyze the participation level among the students.
- To analyze the effective utilization of club activities among students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.

Needs and Importance:

- The club activities provide a setting to become involved and to interact with each others.
- These activities are leading to increase the learning and also enhanced development.
- Club activities are important because students can expand their network which is also beneficial in finding better career development.
- It is also important to develop the particular skills and exhibit their non- academic skills.
- Learning the new things and also developing the personal skills.

Scope of the Study:

- The study covers the importance of club activities in the college premises.
- The study is conducted to create participation level among the students.
- The basic purpose of the study is to analyze the effectiveness of club activities in the college.
- The study also analyzes the effective utilization of club activities among students.

Research Design and Methodology:

The sources of data used in this project report are primary data.

Primary Data:

Primary data consists of original information gathered from the sample size of 110 respondents.

Data Collection:

The data collection tool is used for the research in "Questionnaires" to get the primary data for the research. clear, and testable proposition or predictive statement about the possible outcome of a scientific research study based on a particular property of a population, such as presumed differences between groups on a particular variable or relationships between variables.

Null Hypothesis:

A null hypothesis is a type of hypothesis used in statistics that proposes that there is no difference between certain characteristics of a population (or data-generating process).

Alternative Hypothesis:

An alternative hypothesis states that there is statistical significance between two variables.

Research Design:

A research design is the set of methods and procedures used in collecting and analyzing measures of the variables specified in the problem research. The design of a study defines the study type and sub-type, research problem, hypotheses, independent and dependent variables, experimental design, and, if applicable, data collection methods and a statistical analysis plan. A research design is a framework that has been created to find answers to research questions.

Sample Design:

In the theory of finite population sampling, a sampling design specifies for every possible sample its probability of being drawn.

Sample Size:

The sample size selected for the study is 110 students.

Sample size	-	110
Population size	-	260
Sample area	-	Perambalur
Sample unit	-	Samples are Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College Perambalur.

Statistical Tools of the Study:

Collected data was analyzed with the help of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.

- Percentage analysis
- Chi-Square
- Correlation
- ANOVA

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Participation Level among Students:

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Highly Satisfied	14	12.72
2	Satisfied	73	66.36
3	Neutral	17	15.45
4	Dissatisfied	5	4.54
5	Highly Dissatisfied	1	1
Total		110	100

Inference:

From the above table it is observed that, 12.72% of respondents are highly satisfied with the participation, 66.36% of respondents are satisfied, 15.45% of respondents are neutral, 4.54% of respondents are dissatisfied and 1% of respondents are highly dissatisfied with the participation.

ANOVA Table:

Sources of Variance	SS	DF	MS	F	P - Value
Rows	441.4	4	110	2.67	0.07
Columns	255.4	4	63.8	1.54	0.236
Errors	660.5	1	41.2		
Total	1357				

Degree of freedom = (k-1) (n-k) = 16

For (4, 16) degree of freedom at 5% level of significance , the F test table value is 3.006917

Interpretation:

Calculated value < Tabulated value. Hence Ho is accepted and H1 is rejected.

Conclusion:

There is no significant relation between the satisfaction in club activities and improving the knowledge.

Suggestions:

- The researcher has given the following suggestions to improve the participation level of the students.
- Conducted more activities to improve the participation level of the students.
- Club activities are part of educational process that has to be established among teachers and students.
- Activities should be designed keeping in mind interest, aptitude and the attitude of the students.
- The club leaders should be given the opportunity to attend the activities and conducting the programs to improving their performances.

Conclusion:

Club activities give the students a chance to think box and get creative ideas of their own with the help of a guide or facilitator field trips, excursions, science fair are some of the co-curricular activities. These activities help the students in developing learning experience by giving them a chance to think in new ways to solve a problem or answer a question. These activities also provide an opportunity to the students work in teams and develop the team spirit in them. These activities also encouraging the students to participate and improving the skills and the knowledge.

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